

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/scar
hash://md5/e57ea646f758c244355376b47f1116da

by Nomer, Elton and Preston, three naive review bots
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<https://globalbioticinteractions.org/contribute>
<https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/scar/issues>

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/scar, has fingerprint hash://md5/e57ea646f758c244355376b47f1116da, is 35.1MiB in size and contains 40,904 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., preysOn) between 277 primary taxa (e.g., Krefftichthys) and 1,133 associated taxa (e.g., Fish). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research. (2023). SCAR Southern Ocean Diet and Energetics Database (2023-04-04) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7796465>
 hash://md5/e41e29d8fb3c2d731f292ec08798cf6b hash://md5/05abf23c0b9e5f4bc721ff407455af0a
 hash://sha256/7a344b858ab8d1daeca1da49843e8bf957f1116ff9e10a29176ab5c02cb49bef
<https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/scar/archive/1856664248be16b9dcee9ba56d2b23d87f3d9cd12026-01-24T06:05:02.645Z> hash://md5/e57ea646f758c244355376b47f1116da

For additional metadata related to this dataset, please visit <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/scar> and inspect associated metadata files including, but not limited to, *README.md*, *eml.xml*, and/or *globi.json*.

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like `grep`, `mlr`, `tail` and `head`.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.1
nomer	0.5.17
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 35.1MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/scar

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/scar\
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/scar\
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/scar\
| nomer append col\
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/scar`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/scar`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/scar`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/scar`)

You can find a copy of the full review script at `check-data.sh`. See also GitHub and Codeberg.

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format

filename	description
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

Biotic Interactions

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/scar`, has fingerprint hash://md5/e57ea646f758c244355376b47f1116da, is 35.1MiB in size and contains 40,904 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., `preysOn`) between 277 primary taxa (e.g., `Krefflichthys`) and 1,133 associated taxa (e.g., `Fish`).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in `gzipped csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the `gzipped html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 3: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Pachyptila	preysOn	Crustacea	<p>Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research. (2023). SCAR Southern Ocean Diet and Energetics Database (2023-04-04) [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7796465 hash://md5/e41e29d8fb3c2d731f292ec08798cf6b hash://md5/05abf23c0b9e5f4bc721ff407455af0a hash://sha256/7a344b858ab8d1daeca1da49843e8</p> <p>Accessed at https://github.com/globalbiotici/interactions/scar/archive/1856664248be16b9dcee9ba56d2b23d87f3d9cd1.zip on 28 Jan 2026.</p>

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Pachyptila	preysOn	Euphausia superba	Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research. (2023). SCAR Southern Ocean Diet and Energetics Database (2023-04-04) [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7796465 hash://md5/e41e29d8fb3c2d731f292ec08798cf6b hash://md5/05abf23c0b9e5f4bc721ff407455af0a hash://sha256/7a344b858ab8d1daeca1da49843e8 Accessed at https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/scar/archive/1856664248be16b9dcee9ba56d2b23d87f3d9cd1.zip on 28 Jan 2026.

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Pachyptila	preysOn	Euphausia vallentini	Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research. (2023). SCAR Southern Ocean Diet and Energetics Database (2023-04-04) [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7796465 hash://md5/e41e29d8fb3c2d731f292ec08798cf6b hash://md5/05abf23c0b9e5f4bc721ff407455af0a hash://sha256/7a344b858ab8d1daeca1da49843e8 Accessed at https://github.com/globalbiotici/interactions/scar/archive/1856664248be16b9dcee9ba56d2b23d87f3d9cd1.zip on 28 Jan 2026.

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Pachyptila	preysOn	Euphausia	Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research. (2023). SCAR Southern Ocean Diet and Energetics Database (2023-04-04) [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7796465 hash://md5/e41e29d8fb3c2d731f292ec08798cf6b hash://md5/05abf23c0b9e5f4bc721ff407455af0a hash://sha256/7a344b858ab8d1daeca1da49843e8 Accessed at https://github.com/globalbiotici nteractions/scar /archive/1856664 248be16b9dcee9 ba56d2b23d87f3 d9cd1.zip on 28 Jan 2026.

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
preysOn	40904

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Krefflichthys	6667
Electrona	2801
Trematomus	2313
Gymnoscopelus	2047
Arctocephalus	1492

sourceTaxonName	count
Notothenia	1412
Pygoscelis	1180
Thalassarche	1061
Leptonychotes	1049
Bathylagus	1038
Eudyptes	811
Thalassoica	757
Dissostichus	674
Euphausia	620
Stercorarius	601
Aptenodytes	565
Paraeuchaeta	518
Champscephalus	514
Pachyptila	494

Table 6: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Fish	2133
Euphausia superba	1091
Crustacea	927
Gammaridea	884
Themisto gaudichaudii	796
Calanoides acutus	741
Ostracoda	697
Primno macropa	662
Unidentified	613
Isopoda	605
Vibilia antarctica	588
Rhincalanus gigas	587
Calanus propinquus	583
Calanus simillimus	573
Polychaeta	570
Copepoda	563
Salpida	559
Euphausia triacantha	545
Gastropoda	504

Table 7: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Trematomus	preysOn	Gammaridea	456
Notothenia	preysOn	Gammaridea	338
Krefftichthys	preysOn	Calanus simillimus	321
Krefftichthys	preysOn	Calanoides acutus	321
Krefftichthys	preysOn	Themisto gaudichaudii	321
Krefftichthys	preysOn	Rhincalanus gigas	320
Krefftichthys	preysOn	Ostracoda	320
Krefftichthys	preysOn	Vibilia antarctica	320
Krefftichthys	preysOn	Calanus propinquus	320
Krefftichthys	preysOn	Primno macropa	320
Krefftichthys	preysOn	Salpida	319
Trematomus	preysOn	Residue	291
Trematomus	preysOn	Polychaeta	282
Krefftichthys	preysOn	Metridia	274
Krefftichthys	preysOn	Fish	272
Krefftichthys	preysOn	Thysanoessa	270
Krefftichthys	preysOn	Clausocalanus	269
Krefftichthys	preysOn	Microcalanus	269
Krefftichthys	preysOn	Ctenocalanus	269

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

You can download the indexed dataset under review at [indexed-interactions.csv.gz](#). A tab-separated file can be found at [indexed-interactions.tsv.gz](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at [indexed-interactions.gpkg](#) for point data and [indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg](#) for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at [GloBI website](#), by opening

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 8: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Algae	NONE	col	Algae
Anthropogenic material	NONE	col	Anthropogenic material
Appendicularian pellet	NONE	col	Appendicularian pellet
Carrion	NONE	col	Carrion

Table 9: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	104
col	class	30
col	family	101
col	genus	446
col	gigaclass	1
col	infraorder	3
col	kingdom	5
col	order	32
col	parvorder	1
col	parvphylum	1
col	phylum	21
col	species	518
col	subclass	6
col	subfamily	3
col	subgenus	6
col	suborder	4
col	subphylum	2
col	subspecies	6
col	superfamily	4
col	superorder	4
col	tribe	1
discoverlife	NA	1283
gbif	NA	77
gbif	class	30
gbif	family	103
gbif	form	1
gbif	genus	486
gbif	kingdom	6
gbif	order	33
gbif	phylum	21
gbif	species	541
gbif	subspecies	6
itis	NA	275
itis	class	30
itis	division	4
itis	family	100
itis	genus	423
itis	infrakingdom	1
itis	infraorder	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
itis	kingdom	5
itis	order	33
itis	phylum	15
itis	species	370
itis	subclass	10
itis	subfamily	3
itis	suborder	6
itis	subphylum	4
itis	subspecies	2
itis	superclass	2
itis	superdivision	3
itis	superfamily	1
itis	superorder	1
mdd	NA	1282
ncbi	NA	214
ncbi	clade	8
ncbi	class	33
ncbi	family	101
ncbi	genus	446
ncbi	infraorder	4
ncbi	kingdom	2
ncbi	order	33
ncbi	phylum	17
ncbi	species	402
ncbi	subclass	11
ncbi	subfamily	2
ncbi	suborder	6
ncbi	subphylum	2
ncbi	superclass	1
ncbi	superfamily	3
ncbi	superkingdom	1
ncbi	superorder	3
pdb	NA	848
pdb	class	33
pdb	family	74
pdb	genus	181
pdb	informal	1
pdb	infraclass	1
pdb	infraorder	2
pdb	kingdom	4
pdb	order	33
pdb	phylum	19
pdb	species	67
pdb	subclass	7

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
pbdb	subfamily	1
pbdb	subkingdom	1
pbdb	suborder	8
pbdb	subphylum	1
pbdb	superclass	2
pbdb	superfamily	1
pbdb	superorder	3
pbdb	superphylum	1
pbdb	tribe	1
pbdb	unranked clade	14
tpt	NA	1197
tpt	family	5
tpt	genus	39
tpt	order	1
tpt	species	40
wfo	NA	1273
wfo	genus	9
worms	NA	40
worms	class	33
worms	family	100
worms	genus	464
worms	gigaclass	1
worms	infrakingdom	3
worms	infraorder	4
worms	infraphylum	1
worms	kingdom	5
worms	order	35
worms	parvorder	1
worms	parvphylum	1
worms	phylum	19
worms	phylum (division)	2
worms	species	538
worms	subclass	9
worms	subfamily	7
worms	suborder	6
worms	subphylum	4
worms	subspecies	6
worms	superfamily	4
worms	superorder	5
worms	tribe	1

Table 10: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	108
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1527
col	SYNONYM_OF	97
discoverlife	NONE	1596
gbif	NONE	87
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1766
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	163
itis	NONE	287
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1282
itis	SYNONYM_OF	52
mdd	NONE	1574
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	10
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	1
ncbi	NONE	230
ncbi	SAME_AS	1360
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	25
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	609
pbdb	NONE	1003
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	65
tpt	NONE	1462
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	121
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	2
wfo	NONE	1576
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	4
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	5
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	2
worms	NONE	44
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1566
worms	SYNONYM_OF	63

Table 11: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 12: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-01-28T18:55:01Z	note	source taxon name missing
2026-01-28T18:55:01Z	note	source taxon name missing
2026-01-28T18:55:01Z	note	source taxon name missing
2026-01-28T18:55:01Z	note	source taxon name missing

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 13: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
source taxon name missing	76
target taxon name missing	30

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-01-28) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

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Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

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⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

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